

A case study into Van der Valk on how to process the consequences due to Covid-19

**Joas
Goedegebuur**

j.m.goedegebuur
@uvt.nl

**Dhylan
Simons**

d.t.a.simons
@uvt.nl

**Kris
Brons**

k.s.brons
@uvt.nl

**Harry
Feringa**

h.j.feringa
@uvt.nl

**Jelle
de Gardeijn**

j.degardeijn
@uvt.nl

**Sander
Frencken**

s.j.m.frencken
@uvt.nl

ABSTRACT

In this research, the changes due to Covid-19 in the tourism industry will be described. A before and after March 2020 situation will be described by using the changes in business process integration, IT governance, and cybersecurity. The case study will be in the hotel business, especially on Van der Valk.

Keywords

Covid-19, IT Governance, Business Process Integration, Cybersecurity, Changed Practices Tourism.

INTRODUCTION

An unknown virus was detected in Wuhan, China, late 2019. It was disregarded at first, although warnings came from intelligence services. Wuhan was put into lockdown, but it was already too late. The virus spread globally. Change, chaos, and flexibility are terms that properly reflect the current and turbulent times. Firms are faced with overwhelming, competing challenges and uncharted waters as they continue to navigate the impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic (Accenture, 2020).

There are unprecedented global travel restrictions and stay-at-home orders. These restrictions weaken the global economy in a highly disruptive manner. With limited knowledge and no vaccine to cure the virus, the future does not look bright. Governments issue emergency packages to (try to) save their economies. The restrictions which are enforced by the government have an enormous impact, especially on social lives, communities, and tourism. With global travel restrictions, 90% of the world population is affected and tourism in March simply does not exist (Gösseling, Scott, & Hall, 2020).

Therefore, firms in all kinds of industries are forced to transform their operations and processes to adapt to the changing environment and be more flexible quickly. How? They must transform their business in a digital way (Vial, 2019). In this research paper, the focus lies on the tourism industry since the impact on the tourism sector is enormous. Additionally, to further narrow this topic down, research has been done for the Van der Valk hotel in The Netherlands. Eventually, this research's main objective is to provide Van der Valk hotel with vital information regarding digital transformation during a pandemic. To be more specific, IT governance structures, changing business processes and cybersecurity elements will be analyzed in this paper. Additionally, the digital transformation activities undergone by Van der Valk will be discussed. Subsequently, improvements will be suggested.

RESEARCH

Objective

This research aims to find the changes in the tourism industry, especially for the Dutch hotel organization Van der Valk. Van der Valk had to get used to the changes because of Covid-19. The digital efficiency for customers in the hotels has to improve. Van der Valk wants to optimize the capacity of its hotels through IT. This research contains the knowledge of the use of IT tools and methods for this demand. The research aims to deliver a solution in the digital transformation of the IT of Van der Valk so they can optimize their capacity despite Covid-19 regulations and restrictions.

This has led to the following research question:

“To what extent can the Hotel Industry cope with changing business dynamics due to COVID-19?”

19? A case study of the Dutch hotel chain Van der Valk.”

Approach

This research's approach is at first desk research; academic papers will be used for background research. Knowledge of business process integration, IT governance, and cybersecurity will be gained at first.

The goal is to determine what has changed in the hotel and tourism industry, especially at Van der Valk after Covid-19 introduced itself in March. At the start, the situation before March will be described. The business process integration, IT governance, and cybersecurity state at that moment will be described.

Then the current situation will be described. Information about the current situation will be gathered through interviews with employees at Van der Valk. Preference is given to an IT manager. In these interviews, these employees can describe the situation before and after March. They can explain how they experienced the changes due to Covid-19 and how Van der Valk was digitally transformed. Also, they can provide mistakes, so this research can aim to solve possible issues. This approach aims for business process transformations due to corona, changes in the IT governance, and the cybersecurity's current state at Van der Valk.

HOSPITALITY

The tourism sector and specifically the hotel sector in The Netherlands is a part of horeca. Horeca is an aggregated word that consists of Hotel, Restaurant, and Café. The horeca sector includes 64,185 companies and employs around 813,000 people, of which 498,000 are full time (CBS, 2020). Van der Valk owns 113 hotels globally and 77 in The Netherlands (Valk, 2020). Before the occurrence of the current pandemic, the revenue of the horeca was continually increasing. With 2015 as the primary year (100), and 2014 with a starting point 93.6, the revenue was at its peak in 2019, 128.1. Halfway through 2020, this number decreased drastically to 53.8. The overall tourism sector decreased by around 45% in the first quarter of 2020 (CBS, 2020). Specifically, the hotel sector had a decrease of over 75% in the second quarter of 2020. The restaurants had a decrease of 51.4% in revenue (CBS, 2020).

The tourism sector is a widely influenced sector by crises and events, such as terrorist attacks (2001) and economic crises (2008/2009). None of those crises or events affected the tourism sector long-term (World Bank 2020a, 2020b). These findings would suggest that tourism is a sector that is resistant to major crises. However, COVID-19

pandemic could be different.

It is no question that there is a relationship between globalization and the widespread of a virus to become a pandemic. Due to the increase in mobility of the world population, the spread of influenza and coronaviruses accelerate at a terrifying level (Brown et al., 2016). Thus, tourism contributes to the spread of a virus (Nicolaidis et al., 2019). Given the enormous impact of a pandemic and the relatively high occurrence, three in the twentieth century (Kilbourne, 2006) and four in the twenty-first (WHO, 2020), the research regarding the economic impact is very limited (Fan, Jamison, & Summers, 2018). This might be because the past pandemics did not have a similar implication for the global economy as COVID-19. Before a person has any symptoms, he is already contagious. As a result, measures like physical distance and travel restrictions are made to prevent the virus's spread.

In addition to this, the testing capacity is limited; it is not known who is contagious and who is not. The question raises how long the current measures will be maintained. Since the current measures have significantly impacted the tourism sector negatively and, thus, the hotel sector. The impact of the current pandemic is illustrated in Figure 1. Figure 1 displays the difference between the occupation of the accommodation sector in the week of 21 March in 2020 and 2019, the numbers have declined by 50% or more. The countries that are impacted the most by the virus, are the ones that were hit the hardest by a decline in tourism World Bank 2020a).

Figure 1: Occupation of accommodations week 21 2019-2020 (World Bank, 2020a)

Due to the low tourism numbers, many hotels closed and experienced a significant decline in revenue. At this moment, it is not precisely clear how hotels and their restaurants can recover from this. It might be possible for large hotel chains to reconsider their supply chains. An advantage of big hotel chains is that they are not limited in their financial liquidity and small profit margins. So, a lot more alternatives are possible (Gösseling, Scott, & Hall, 2020).

ANALYSIS

IT governance and strategic sourcing

With Governance and Strategic Sourcing the focus will be on the customer journey in particular. The comparison here will be more on a global level than business process integration, where a process, in particular, is enlarged for discussion. For Van der Valk and their sector, this research aims at IT-business alignment.

In this IT Governance part of this research, the before March situation will be described at first. Then the situation after the outbreak will be described. Also, the business changes and IT will be provided through the IT governance patterns diagram.

During the changing environment caused by COVID-19, Van der Valk needs to digitally transform their business by linking new IT systems to desirable business outcomes. To do so, Van der Valk needs to manage its IT governance and strategic sourcing. Newly introduced systems, combined with a couple of IT investments which Van der Valk can focus on are:

- Automating the check-in of a customer;
- Unlocking doors of rooms by a customer by use of their phone;
- Keeping the floor capacity at 20 percent.

To benefit from the IT investments, Van der Valk needs to focus on how IT should be governed at the moment and how this should be changed under the current business environment.

The first step of coping with COVID-19 is analyzing the environment. This is an important step since the extent of turbulence decides which model you should use in order to cope with this environment. With models is meant for instance Resource Based View, the model of Porter or Dynamic Capabilities Diagram. So, in which type of environment is Van der Valk situated? Looking at the turbulence scheme levels (Ansoff & McDonnell, 1990), Van der Valk is situated in turbulence levels four or five of figure 2. The reason for selecting these levels is due to this virus's partially predictable and global socio-political characteristics.

Environmental Turbulence	Repetitive	Expanding	Changing	Discontinuous	Surprising
Complexity	National		Regional		Global
	Economic		Technological		Socio-Political
Familiarity of events	Familiar	Extrapolable		Discontinuous	Discontinuous
	Novel				
Rapidity of change	Slower than response		Comparable to response		Faster than response
Visibility of future surprises	Recurring	Forecastable	Predictable	Partially Predictable	Unpredictable
Turbulence Level	1	2	3	4	5

Figure 2: Turbulence levels Ansoff, H. I., & McDonnell, E. J. (1990)

Analyzing the IT-governance situation of Van der Valk pre-Covid-19, there can be concluded that they utilize a two-party decision-making approach involving IT executives and a group of business leaders representing the operating units. Taking this into account, Van der Valk is currently (pre-COVID-19) using a feudal approach for every type of decision-making (Van der Valk, 2020). The reason for selecting this approach corresponds to the strategy of Van der Valk. Van der Valk focuses on sustainable hospitality (Hotel Hoorn, 2020). Van der Valk maximizes local responsiveness since business units or process leaders make separate decisions based on the unit or process needs to utilize hospitality to the maximum (Weill & Woodham, 2002). The IT governance archetype feudal approach corresponds to the third arrangement of IT governance patterns. Arrangement 3 is most effective in firms with different business units, where profitability or cost control is a predominant issue. Van der Valk is a hotel chain with 77 business units - or better known - locations in The Netherlands.

Due to the current pandemic, the revenues of Van der Valk decreased significantly. Van der Valk is the largest Dutch hospitality chain in The Netherlands and, at the head of the chain, is a board of directors. Since 2000 the chain has been a franchise, and in 2011 “Valk Exclusive” was founded as a separate part of Van der Valk. Like the website and loyalty program, some activities are still centrally arranged (Van der Valk, 2020). This indicates that Van der Valk has business leaders who make well-informed decisions and are sensible for significant changes and mergers. As cost control is a predominant issue due to COVID-19 in the Hotel Industry, it can be recommended that Van der Valk uses arrangement 3 of the IT governance pattern in the post-COVID-19 situation. This arrangement, seen in figure 3, is also suitable when major changes are occurring.

Figure 3: IT governance pattern Van der Valk

Business process integration

The process used for examination is the book and checking-in of/in Van der Valk. The described situations are pre- and post-situation of this process. Last, the challenges for Van der Valk in the period of COVID-19 examined. These three subchapters describe the digital transformation Van der Valk went through.

Pre-situation

Imagine the summer in 2019. You are going on vacation with your family or friends and arrive at your hotel to check-in. You are greeted at the reception, and by partly digital and partly face-to-face, you get checked in. The check-in process focuses on customer service and, where possible, humans are added as a resource. Where it is possible to book and check-in can be done online, Van der Valk focusses by adding value through his employees working in their assets.

Post-situation

Where normally, smaller-size firms are more agile in adjusting to the changing environmental conditions and are, consequently, performing better (Olsen, M. D., Murthy, B., & Teare, R., 1994). Covid-19 changed the business entirely, now big-sized firms, like Van der Valk, did not have a choice and needed to show that the organization is agile. Where mostly all activities were focused on adding value as customer services in a face-to-face presentation, Van der Valk had to digitize their activities. Where the booking was already mostly digitized, checking-in had to change entirely. In a short amount of time, there had to be a completely new system, new interfaces for usage, and servers must be upgraded to manage larger amounts of digital traffic. New systems had to be implemented for the checking-process. Van der Valk implemented a service robot for check-in and -out for customers. They could still implement their high graded customer service, which customers highly appreciated and why they mostly choose Van der Valk. The robot increases customer service efficiently because they add an interaction level to customers in a way that is still acceptable in regards of the requirements which the RIVM demanded.

Challenges

A key challenge for these organizations has been maintaining organizational culture in remote environments (Barnes, S. J., 2020). To capitalize on the opportunity for digitization, firms need to be agile and rapidly develop capabilities that can help them survive the changes that the environment imposes upon them (Seetharaman, P., 2020). So for Van der Valk, the main challenges are maintaining their organizational culture and rapidly shifting to an agile environment.

Van Der Valk combined agile thinking and keeping their culture by implementing and starting

with the service robots. By sufficient efficiencies, they met the challenge of agile development of their digitalization and corporal culture. The goal of accelerating the digitization is to improve the customer experience during COVID-19 and also be ready for post COVID-19.

Cybersecurity

For Van der Valk, cybersecurity is getting more and more critical. With the growing use of IT-systems in their company, they will face some security challenges and their customers' privacy they have not experienced before, like someone trying to hack those systems.

Especially in these challenging times, Van der Valk needs to adopt new changes in their business quickly. As discussed, before using a new automated check-in system and unlocking system for the rooms called Mobile Key.

This new key system is also bringing unknown risks to the hotel. What if a stranger can open a room at any time, the hotel cannot guarantee its customers' safety and belongings. According to F-secure research, all electronic lock systems of any hotel worldwide can be exploited to gain access to a room by an attacker. (F-secure, 2018) With the use of new technologies, this will only increase.

To ensure that their newly launched Mobile Key would be safe to use in the hotels, they did a hackathon in 2017. In this hackathon, they asked hackers to test their new online check-in and Mobile Key system. The hotel wants to be open to the goodwill of security researchers who help security moving forward. (Valk, 2020)

Identity theft is one of the most significant risks for hotels nowadays. A hotel stores a lot of data from its customers, like names, email addresses, addresses, passports, and payment information. This could be interesting for hackers. In the past, there were already some big hacks in hotels providing hackers with a lot of data.

(HotelNewsNow, 2020)

Hotels are depending on wireless communication; customers are expecting that they can connect to the hotel's (free) WIFI network. These networks also create new opportunities for cybercriminals. Many of the customers will not realize that they might be at risk when they use these WIFI networks, but there are real threats. Hackers could use a Man-in-the-Middle attack or the Dark hotel malware, for example. (Shabani, 2016)

Risk analyses

For Van der Valk, there are risks regarding cybersecurity that will be clarified in a risk assessment. These risks are shown in table 1 and will

be evaluated using a risk matrix, as shown in figure 5. In this matrix, the impact (negligible to severe) and likelihood (very unlikely to very likely) will get a score of 1 to 5. The complete Risk analyses can be found in appendix A.

Risk	
1	Identity theft of customer data
2	Ransomware attack on the hotel systems
3	Dark hotel attack
4	The electronic lock of a room will be hacked.
5	DDoS Attack on the main systems
6	Phishing attack on customers

Table 1: Risks for Van der Valk

The OWASP risk-rating method will be used to describe the risks and score the likelihood of the impact of each risk. This risk-rating method uses the following treat source factors to analyse a treat: Skill level, motivate, opportunity, and size. These factors will be rated on a score of 0 to 9. (Refsdal, Solhaug & Stølen, 2015)

First, the risks for Van der Valk will be described and scored using the OWASP method, next the risk will be put into the risk matrix.

		Impact				
		Negligible	Minor	Moderate	Significant	Severe
Likelihood	Very Likely	Low Med	Medium	Med Hi	High	High
	Likely	Low	Low Med	Medium	Med Hi	High
	Possible	Low	Low Med	Medium	Med Hi	Med Hi
	Unlikely	Low	Low Med	Low Med	Medium	Med Hi
	Very Unlikely	Low	Low	Low Med	Medium	Medium

Figure 5: Risk matrix

The impact of COVID-19

With the ongoing pandemic, Van der Valk is facing some challenges to ensure the safety of its customers. For example, they need to find a way to monitor how people are moving and how they can safeguard the 1,5 meters inside their hotels and protect their customers' privacy and respect the GDPR. The same counts for the registration obligation for bars and restaurants by the Dutch government. This introduced new risks regarding the safe storage of data in a short period.

Van der Valk needed to adapt fast to this new situation and provide all their hotels with a safe system to store it and be assured that the data is safely stored. The fast implementation of such a system can be hard and challenging.

In this case, it is also essential to see what the GDPR states about this kind of data storage and if it is a hotel is allowed to store this data about their

customers.

Article 4 of the GDPR ("Data concerning health") states that personal data related to a person's physical or mental health needs higher protection. Information from a self-check survey that people need to fill in before visiting a restaurant can be placed under article 4. (Becker et al., 2020)

The key principle of data protection is that personal data needs to be processed lawfully. This means that an organization needs a legal base to process such data.

Measures to prevent the risks

Some measures can be taken into account to reduce the risks that are described in the risk analyses. Some of these measures will be expressed below.

One of the most important measures is the training of staff to prevent and recognize security risks. They need to be aware of ongoing threats and how to avoid them. An element of this training can be to identify malicious emails to prevent a ransomware attack from happening. (NCSC, 2020)

To prevent guests from phishing attacks, Van der Valk has launched a website where they explain how to recognize an email from them and some examples of phishing emails sent in their company's name. (Valk, 2020)

As described before, Van der Valk did a hackathon to test how safe their new mobile key system was. This is an excellent way to test if the systems are designed as they are supposed to be. (Valk, 2020)

DISCUSSION

This paper aimed to research the consequences of Covid-19 in the tourism industry. This paper focused on how the Hotel Industry can cope with changing business dynamics due to COVID-19? To answer this question, research was done into Van der Valk hotels.

The influence of IT, in this case, was investigated through three aspects namely, IT governance, business process integration, and cybersecurity.

The IT governance perspective describes that Van der Valk needs to digitally transform their business by linking new IT systems to desirable business outcomes. As described before, it can be recommended to use arrangement 3 of the IT governance pattern.

The business process perspective needed to change the check-in process entirely to make it suitable for the pandemic we face today. This process was designed to focus on human contacts, and in the new situation, it needed to be contactless to protect the employees and guests. The main challenges are maintaining their organizational culture and rapidly shifting to an agile environment.

The cybersecurity perspective shows that these fast adopted changes can bring new risks to the hotel they have not experienced before or change the likelihood of risks. So will unlocking rooms of rooms by a customer by using their phone introduce extra options for hackers to hack the electronic lock.

Due to the pandemic, Van der Valk needs to implement these changes much faster than in regular times. Thus, they cannot spend as much time on research as which system would fit them the best as they would typically do. This could lead to more security risks in the short term or that they need to make significant adjustments to make it also suitable for a long time.

CONCLUSION

THIS RESEARCH FOCUSES ON HOW VAN DER VALK COULD ADAPT TO THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC IN A FAST MANNER AND REDUCE THE IMPACT ON THEIR BUSINESS BY USING NEW TECHNOLOGIES AND CHANGING THEIR BUSINESS PROCESSES. THIS PAPER DESCRIBED HOW THEY CAN IMPLEMENT THESE TECHNOLOGIES, HOW THE BUSINESS PROCESS WILL CHANGE, AND WHAT RISKS THEY CAN EXPECT. THE MAIN POINT IS WHAT THEY CAN CHANGE NOW TO MAKE SURE THEY CAN REMAIN IN OPERATION. BY IMPLEMENTING THE ADVISED SOLUTIONS IN THIS PAPER, THEY CAN REDUCE THE IMPACT TO A MINIMUM AND STAY IN BUSINESS TO THE BEST EXTENT.

BECAUSE THIS PAPER IS WRITTEN IN THE MIDDLE OF THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC, IT FOCUSED ONLY ON THE SHORT TERM. THESE CHANGES WILL MEAN IN THE LONG RUN NOT PART OF THIS RESEARCH AND NOT DESCRIBED IN THIS PAPER.

IN FURTHER RESEARCH, IT WILL BE GOOD TO FOCUS MORE ON THE EFFECTS OF THE CRISIS ON VAN DER VALK IN THE NEAR FUTURE. IT WILL ALSO BE INTERESTING TO RESEARCH IF THEY ADAPT TO THE PANDEMIC IN THE RIGHT WAY AND LEARN FOR IT FOR THE NEXT CRISIS AFFECTING THEIR BUSINESS.

THIS RESEARCH SHOWS THAT TO COME TO A GOOD SOLUTION, IT IS ESSENTIAL TO LOOK AT THE DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION AS A WHOLE. BY DOING SO, YOU WILL SEE THAT IT INFECTS THE BUSINESS PROCESSES, BUSINESS MODEL, AND CULTURE IN AN ORGANIZATION, AND NOT ONLY ONE OF THESE.

APPENDIX

Appendix A: Risk analysis

Risk 1: Identity theft of customer data

Impact: 5 Likelihood: 4

The primary source of this threat is black hat hackers. These hackers' skill levels can be high, so we score them with a seven for skill level. The motive for them is to obtain a lot of personal data of the customers of a hotel. This is a powerful motive so that it will be scored with an eight.

To perform a hack like this, a hacker would need to know about hacking and the opportunity to find weaknesses inside the systems, which he can exploit. So for this threat, there is an opportunity score of eight. The size of this group is not that big, so that it will be scored with a six. The average of this score equals 7.25. This makes the threat level high, and the likelihood would be scored as likely.

As stated before, Van der Valk owns quite a lot of hotels(119 globally), so the impact would be severe when an attack on their systems succeeded. This will place the risk in the red area of the risk matrix. (Panai, 2018)

Risk 2: Ransomware attack on the hotel systems

Impact: 5 Likelihood: 3

A ransomware attack is carried out by malware that a user installs on their computer system and will lock the system(s) until the creator is paid. These kinds of attacks' skill levels are scored with a seven since a hacker needs to be skilled in developing such malware. This threat's motive will be scored with a six since they only try to make money with this kind of malware.

To succeed in a ransomware attack, the attack's target needs to open a specific file, so the opportunity for this threat depends on the knowledge of this person. It is scored with a six. The size of this threat is quite significant since it can be targeted to many people and companies at the same time, so it will be scored with an eight. The average score for this threat equals 6.75. The threat level is medium, and the likelihood is scored possibly.

The hotel cannot function without its systems, so the impact of a ransomware attack would be severe if the attackers could block overall key systems. This will place this risk in the orange area of the risk matrix.

Risk 3: Dark hotel attack

Impact: 5 Likelihood: 5

The risk of WIFI hacking would be exploited by black hat hackers. The skill level of these hackers is high, so we score them with a seven again. The

motive is to obtain a lot of personal data of the customers. This motive is powerful so that it will be scored with an eight.

A hacker needs to be inside a hotel to get access to the network to perform a hack like this, and they need to set it up in each hotel. So the opportunity that this would happen is not that high, it will be scored with a four. The size of this threat is not that big as well, since it occurs locally. So the size is achieved with a four. The average of this score equals 5.75. This makes the threat level medium, and the likelihood would be scored as likely. Since this would happen locally, is the impact moderate. This will place this risk in the orange area of the risk matrix. (Shabani, 2016)

Risk 4: The electronic lock of a room will be hacked.

Impact: 7 Likelihood: 4

As described before in this paper, there is the possibility that someone else than the customer would get access to a room. The main source will be a black hat hacker or someone who buys this technology on the black market. The skill level of a hacker can be high, so we score it with a seven. For a buyer, this will be low, so it will be scored with a two. The motive will be to steal the belongings of a customer, this will be scored with a seven.

To get this to work the attacker needs to be inside the hotel, which will decrease the opportunity, so it is scored with a four. This brings the average score to a four. This makes the threat level low, and the likelihood will be scored as unlikely. This attack will adequately work in Van der Valk hotels if they can succeed in one hotel so that the impact will be significant. This will place the risk in the yellow area of the risk matrix.

Risk 5: DDoS Attack on the main systems

Impact: 9 Likelihood: 7

A DDoS attack can be made by a cyber-terrorist or just a script-kiddie who did buy a script online. The skill level for a cyber-terrorist is scored with a seven and for a script-kiddie with a two. This treat's motive will be scored with a one for a script-kiddie and an eight for a cyber-terrorist. The opportunity for this attack would be a seven for both attackers. The size is a seven for a script-kiddie, who can easily perform an attack from home and a three for a cyber-terrorist since there are not that many of them. The average equals 4.25 for a script-kiddie and a 6.25. Based on this score, the likelihood would be estimated to be likely. The impact of this threat would be severe since all systems can't be used during an attack. This will place the risk in the red area of the risk matrix.

Risk 6: Phishing attack on customers

Impact: 4

Likelihood: 8

A phishing attack is not that hard to exploit, so the skill level will be scored with a three. The motive is to steal money from customers, so it will be scored with an eight. The opportunity would be also high since it can be done from all over the world, so it is scored with a nine. The size is really big since they target all customers, so the score would be also a nine. The average score for this treat equals 7.25. The likelihood will be likely. The impact for the company would be minor since it does not affect the business itself, but only the customers. This will place the risk in the light green area of the risk matrix.

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